

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CONFLICT ADMINISTRATIVE IN THE REPUBLIC OF KOSOVO

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ABSTRACT

Through this article, I will specify the characteristics of the administrative conflict in Kosovo, where I will make a basic analysis of its operation, the purposes of legal protection of specific quality. The law on administrative conflict in the Republic of Kosovo is to ensure the protection of data judgment . legal interests are different physical, legal and other parties, which are rights and interests with individual decisions or with the responsibilities of public administration bodies, it also has nothing to do with Law No. 03/L-202 regulates the competences, the composition of the court and the rules of the competent rules, the decision of the courts on the legality of the administrative acts by which the competent bodies of the public administration decide on the rights, responsibilities and legal interests. physical and other parties, as well as for the legality of the laws of administrative bodies. The understanding of the administrative conflict is the basic element of this manuscript as it is used to analyze how the legal aspect is protected in the legal form, always being established in the normative acts, the protection of legality is its basic element. Also, through this paper, we will analyze one aspect and objective of the administrative conflict, as well as the full jurisdiction of the administrative conflict.

Keywords: Administrative conflict; Characteristics of administrative conflict; types of administrative conflicts; legality; the law 006Fn administrative conflict; legal and natural persons.

1. Introduction

The understanding of the administrative conflict as well as the most complete protection of the legality of administrative acts can only provide a real judicial control. The court is able to evaluate the legality of administrative activity exercises as well as to observe the cases when the legal norm is violated or not. Judicial protection does not weaken administrative control, but in restoring its right to the truth when the administrative control itself has failed to effectively and efficiently guarantee the legality of administrative acts. The point is legality in the function of public authorities and those responsible for the legal administration for citizens, for the protection of the right to human rights. without bias and information by law. The administrative conflict allows the parties to present their positions through an adversarial debate. Administrative conflict occurs between families and public administration bodies, or they have said changes, between subjects that issue administrative acts which in that case manifest the power of those subjects that occurred in the country subject to the administrative legal change. Therefore, the court in the administrative conflict, authoritatively objectively and professionally the disputed administrative issue.³

By means of the administrative conflict, two basic and mutually related goals are realized

- On the one hand, the administrative conflict has the purpose of realizing and defining the principles of legality in relation to the administration (objective purpose). Strengthening the legality in the changes of the administration, namely by avoiding illegality in relation to the administration, to improve the work of the administration.⁴

- On the other hand, the administrative conflict has the goal of achieving the most complete protection of all subjects of cases and legal actions of events by law, from the infringements of events that can be done to them in the case of issuing administrative acts.⁵

Administrative conflicts arise from administrative legal members in the case with the administrative case act of the authorization body or of works which are public authorizations, it is related to the detriment of the individual or the legal person, in favor of the individual or the entire legal person. . The administrative conflict is the conflict between the individual or legal entity on the one hand and another body on the other hand, and which is the competent court.

The right to start the administrative conflict has a natural person or a legal person if they consider the administrative act to be a matter of right or direct personal interest of a law. The Ombudsman can also fill the administrative conflict, if the administrative act is to the detriment of the social community, in relation to the society he protects it based on the law.

2. CHARACTERISTICS AND TYPES OF ADMINISTRATIVE CONFLICTS

In the techniques of administrative justice, some differences are recognized in the most pronounced administrative conflicts: objective and subjective administrative conflicts; Conflicts on the legality of the administrative act; Full Jurisdiction Conflicts. Subjective and objective administrative conflicts. In distinguishing some conflicts the purpose as well as the type of act. Based on the conflict of the conflict, the subjective administrative solution aims at the protection of the subjective right and the subjective legal nature, while the objective administrative solution has to solve the objective legal changes. The types of acts on which the administrative conflict is located are administrative in the nature of the subject in those cases when the objects are administrative (individual) acts where the individual interest is affected, while objective administrative conflicts are those conflicts that can be opened against general acts. Normative), the general interest on. The conflict over the legality of administrative acts, in the general administrative rules, occur in some cases of conflicts over the illegality of any administrative act. Here we are talking about that conflict when the court decides to decide only the question of the legality of the contested administrative act. In the conflict over the legality of the judicial act, it assesses whether the conflicting administrative act is in a material or formal sense. In this conflict, the court does not deal with this established legal issue, but only with its legality. In such conflicts, the court decision does not have direct legal effects, but its execution in its competence of the body, its act is successful. conflict actions on the legality of the administrative act, the annulment of that act, if it is observed that it is illegal. Therefore, this conflict is also called a related administrative conflict. In this conflict, in the first place,

the illegality of what the administrative act has done is pointed out. In other words, the conflict for the legality of the administrative act consists in the annulment of the attacked administrative act of the lawsuit in the competent court (Basic Court in Pristina-Department for Administrative Affairs), in which case such administrative act does not continue. to produce effects. legal for other parties was dedicated to them. The administrative body had previously issued the annulled act in conflict, it is forced to issue another administrative act that operates from the decision that adjudicates the judgment with which the previous act is. Although, there is a conflict of legality of the administrative act even in case of silence of the administration, in which case the court orders the competent administrative body to issue the relevant act for the parties. It should also be noted that the opening of the administrative conflict is the exhaustion of regular appeal procedures related to the administrative act, if an act is not permissible for this procedure. An important issue at the beginning of the administrative conflict is whether the opening of this conflict has a suspensive effect on the execution of the final act in the administrative procedure, or not. In relation to this issue, the current law on administrative conflicts offers a solution, which states that in case of not granting the suspensive effect for the execution of the administrative act attacked with a lawsuit for administrative conflict, it may cause damage to the parties in the process, then at the request of the plaintiff, the court can give a suspensive effect to such a lawsuit for the execution of the administrative act. In an opposite case, the lawsuit for the opening of the administrative conflict will not have a suspensive effect. So in this type of conflict, the legality of the administrative act is examined, where the objective of the court is to force the administrative body to issue a legal and fair act for the parties. Given that not every time this objective of the court is achieved through the administration body, then the theory of law and administrative procedure but also the legislation in force recognizes the other type of administrative conflict, namely the conflict of full jurisdiction.

3. CONFLICT OF COMPLETE JURISDICTION

Based on the totality of administrative acts in legal systems in some countries, in those cases that are not subjective and objective rights.⁶ This conflicts with the solution that aims to protect subjective and objective rights. In this case, it should be noted that conflicts of jurisdiction are diverse in positive legal systems in several languages. In the full legal conflict, the court decides the dispute. He, the court can decide according to its amendment, not only the legality but also the opportunity of the contested administrative act.⁷ In conclusion, court decisions are related to the conflict in the legal conflict of administrative acts. This happens because of such a conflict, the court is not limited only to the cancellation of the administrative act, but finally solved the specific administrative issue itself.⁸ In contrast to the conflict over the legality of the administrative act, in the conflict of jurisdiction the administrative issue has been completed and the administrative act before the competent court, is not within the authority of the administrative body to decide. So in another such body, the court takes the tax just as it itself decides on the administrative case and its decision has the character of the act.⁹

This type of conflict occurs when the body related to the administration, which previously issued the act attacked with a lawsuit for administrative conflict, respectively, the body which

was silent by not issuing any administrative act, does not adhere to the requirements of the court decision issued in the conflict. of the conduct of the act as the party remains unsatisfied, in which case once again (that is, after the conflict of the legality of the administrative act) it is the fault of the administrative conflict in the competent court, to the same act or to the same inaction-silence of the administration and now the power to decide on the issue of administration from the administration to the court.

CONCLUSIONS

By means of the administrative conflict, we come to the conclusion that the administrative conflict can only be filled against the administrative act of the administrative review at the second level; The conflict can also be filed against the administrative act of the first degree, against which in the administrative procedure the appeal is not allowed. The administrative conflict can be completed even when the competent body has not taken into account the administrative act according to the request or complaint of the parties, under the conditions of the state with this law, these are also defined by the legislation in force, Law No. 03/L-202 on administrative conflicts, as well as the courts in the administrative decision on the legality of administrative acts, with which the administration bodies, in the exercise of public authorizations, decide on the rights, obligations and legal interests of the physical and legal conflict. in administrative matters. By means of this manuscript, I conclude that the right to start the administrative conflict is a natural person as well as a legal entity, if it assesses that with the administrative act in the administrative procedure, the violated person has no right or legal interest, as well as the administrative body, the lawyer of the People, associations and other organizations, which act in defense of public interests to defeat the administrative conflict, these have the right in the administrative conflict, against the decision, which was taken based on the complaint in the administrative procedures, if he/she thinks that it is violated his right or interest.

Also characteristic of the administrative conflict is the competent prosecutor or the authorized person if the administrative act violated the law to the detriment of the central government bodies and other bodies to their detriment, to the local self-government bodies and to their detriment. when the rights of the bodies are violated, conflicts can be initiated administratively. While the administrative conflict, according to the indictment, is resolved by the Supreme Court of the Republic of Kosovo and the judgments of the courts, issued in administrative conflicts, are binding.

References

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